

Certificate of Calibration

THERMOMETERS
17298E, 19868E, 20399E

This certificate is issued in accordance with the laboratory accreditation requirements of the United Kingdom Accreditation Service. It provides traceability of measurement to the SI system of units and/or to units of measurement realised at the National Physical Laboratory or other recognised national metrology institutes. This certificate may not be reproduced other than in full, except with the prior written approval of the issuing laboratory.

FOR: FAAM Airborne Laboratory
Building 146
Central Avenue
Cranfield
Bedfordshire
MK43 0AL

For the attention of Jack Farr

DESCRIPTION: Three 50 Ω platinum resistance thermometers (PRTs)

IDENTIFICATION: Type: E102BL (Loom), E102BL (Plate), E102AL (Loom)
Serial No: 17298E, 19868E, 20399E

DATES OF CALIBRATION: 20 January 2023 to 24 January 2023

Reference: 2022110421-2

Date of issue: 9 February 2023

Checked by: *K Douglas*

Signed:
Name: Mr P A Carroll

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(Authorised Signatory)
on behalf of NPLML

This certificate is consistent with the capabilities that are included in Appendix C of the MRA drawn up by the CIPM. Under the MRA, all participating institutes recognise the validity of each other's calibration and measurement certificates for the quantities, ranges and measurement uncertainties specified in Appendix C (for details see <http://www.bipm.org>).

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MEASUREMENTS

The thermometers were calibrated in a test chamber, in air, by comparison against reference platinum resistance thermometers (PRTs). The test thermometers were fully immersed inside the test chamber.

Traceability of measurement was provided by calibration of the reference thermometers to the International Temperature Scale of 1990 (ITS-90) through NPL Temperature Standards. As requested the PRTs were monitored using a precision resistance bridge with traceability to national standards, using an excitation current of 2.8 mA. At each generated condition a time of not less than 60 minutes was allowed for temperature to equilibrate. A set of 10 readings recorded at 2 minute intervals was then taken from the instruments under test.

The values of the applied conditions are shown in the first column of the table below. The values measured from the instruments under test are then quoted with their equivalent expanded uncertainties, shown in degrees Celsius. This quoted uncertainty relates to the period of the calibration and is not an indication of the long-term stability of the instruments.

The ambient conditions in the NPL humidity laboratory were $23\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and less than 80 % relative humidity.

Applied Condition Measured Temperature	Test Thermometers			
	Measured Resistance of PRT Serial Number 17298E	Measured Resistance of PRT Serial Number 19868E	Measured Resistance of PRT Serial Number 20399E	Expanded Uncertainty of the Temperature Measurement
$^{\circ}\text{C}$	Ω	Ω	Ω	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
-60.02 #	38.294	38.186	38.052	0.08
-50.01 #	40.341	40.190	40.086	0.08
-40.02	42.376	42.182	42.108	0.08
-30.00	44.412	44.173	44.130	0.08
-20.20	46.395	46.114	46.101	0.05
-10.16	48.423	48.096	48.116	0.05
+0.03	50.473	50.097	50.149	0.05
+10.06	52.484	52.061	52.147	0.05
+19.96	54.464	53.995	54.115	0.05
+29.90	56.447	55.929	56.083	0.05
+39.98	58.450	57.884	58.073	0.05
+50.09	60.454	59.838	60.063	0.05

NOTE: # Points below $-40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ are outside the range of both NPL's UKAS accreditation and approved Calibration and Measurement Capabilities (CMCs) under the International Committee for Weights and Measures Mutual Recognition Arrangement (CIPM MRA) for air temperature calibration.

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UNCERTAINTIES

The standard uncertainty of the applied condition represents a combination of the uncertainties arising from calibration and estimated stability of the reference standards, and from the method of transfer to the instrument under test.

The standard uncertainty of measurement is calculated by combining the uncertainty of the applied condition, the resolution of the instrument and its standard deviation for the period of the test. An uncertainty contribution has been included for rounding to give results an equivalent resolution of 0.01 °C.

The reported expanded uncertainty is based on a standard uncertainty multiplied by a coverage factor $k = 2$, providing a coverage probability of approximately 95 %. The uncertainty evaluation has been carried out in accordance with UKAS requirements.

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